

Model Inventori dalam Logistik Kemanusiaan: Sebuah Studi Awal

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Abstrak

Masalah utama dalam bidang logistik bencana adalah ketidakpastian permintaan dalam hal waktu dan lokasi. Sebuah bencana akan menciptakan terjadinya permintaan secara tiba-tiba dalam jumlah yang sangat besar dan *lead time* yang pendek untuk berbagai macam barang dan perlengkapan. Tantangan yang dihadapi dalam situasi ini adalah mengelola pengiriman yang memadai dan tepat waktu. Kendalanya adalah kurangnya sumber daya seperti pasokan, tenaga relawan, ketersediaan teknologi, kapasitas transportasi, dan anggaran. Peran sistem pendukung keputusan menjadi sangat diperlukan untuk membantu para pengambil kebijakan dan keputusan dalam menyusun rencana operasi kemanusiaan yang lebih baik. Tujuan dari studi ini adalah mengembangkan model inventori pada logistik kemanusiaan sebagai sistem pendukung keputusan. Model yang dikembangkan bertujuan untuk mengkoordinasikan operasional dari pusat pasokan utama ke pusat-pusat distribusi di daerah yang terkena bencana. Tujuannya adalah untuk meminimalkan keterlambatan dalam memberikan komoditas diprioritaskan. metodologi dinamika sistem dikembangkan untuk membantu pengambilan keputusan yang kompleks dalam bidang logistik kemanusiaan. Kompleksitas masalah logistik kemanusiaan mengharuskan pentingnya studi awal sebagai kerangka kerja pengembangan system pendukung keputusan untuk pengelolaan inventori barang dan peralatan. Studi ini menerapkan *system dynamics* sebagai pendekatan untuk membangun kebijakan inventori dalam logistik kemanusiaan. Hasil dalam studi ini adalah model awal yang masih perlu dikembangkan lebih lanjut dengan berbagai situasi yang lebih spesifik.

Kata kunci: logistik kemanusiaan, inventori, system dynamics, sistem pendukung keputusan

Pendahuluan

Menurut Ergun et al. (2009) diperkirakan telah terjadi sekitar 6.637 bencana alam antara tahun 1974 dan 2003 di seluruh dunia dengan banyak orang yang terkena dampak lebih dari 5,1 miliar, sekitar 182 juta tunawisma, 2 juta orang meninggal, dan kerugian dilaporkan sekitar USD 1,38 triliun USD. Disebutkan pula bahwa dibandingkan dengan terjadinya bencana di tahun 2005 saja, lebih dari 180.000 kematian dan kerugian ekonomi USD 200.000.000.000. Balcik dan Beamon (2008) menyatakan bahwa rata-rata jumlah tahunan bencana meningkat 55% dan bencana mempengaruhi 33% lebih banyak orang selama 2000-2004 dari selama 1995-1999.

Beberapa jenis bencana yang mendapatkan perhatian dunia dimana kejadiannya di luar Indonesia seperti serangan teroris pada 11 September (2001), tsunami di Asia Selatan (2004), Badai Katrina (2005), gempa bumi bencana di Pakistan (2005), tsunami di Jepang (2011) hanya beberapa contoh dalam beberapa tahun terakhir. Bencana alam yang terjadi

di Indonesia seperti tsunami di Aceh (2004), gempa bumi di Jawa (2006) dan Sumatera Barat (2009). Indonesia adalah salah satu negara di Asia yang termasuk memiliki risiko tinggi bencana alam seperti gempa bumi, tsunami, banjir dan tanah longsor. Lebih khusus, provinsi Sumatera Barat telah menjadi salah satu provinsi yang memiliki risiko tertinggi dari ancaman bencana alam khususnya gempa dan potensi tsunami.

Lee et al. (2009) menjelaskan bahwa rantai pasokan kemanusiaan berbeda dengan rantai pasokan komersial dalam banyak hal karena banyak hal yang tidak diketahui yang dipicu oleh ketidakpastian. Konsekuensi dari pengelolaan logistik kemanusiaan dalam perencanaan distribusi yang tidak efektif adalah kematian, penyakit dan gangguan sosial. Sebuah rencana respons yang lebih baik akan mengurangi jumlah korban tewas. Menurut Gu (2011) faktor utama yang berpengaruh dalam pasokan bantuan adalah prakiraan permintaan darurat, waktu tempuh dari titik layanan ke tempat pengungsian dan kapasitas kendaraan transportasi. Oleh karena itu, perencanaan yang cermat dari distribusi bantuan darurat harus mempertimbangkan berbagai faktor risiko dan ketidakpastian karena logistik kemanusiaan berkenaan dengan kehidupan banyak orang. Tugas menyediakan bantuan bagi para korban bencana dan bantuan pemulihan pasca bencana memerlukan koordinasi antara lokal dan pemerintah federal.

Isu utama dalam logistik kemanusiaan seperti proses pengiriman distribusi dan pelayanan terdiri dari dua jenis saluran adalah saluran distribusi utama dan saluran distribusi lokal (Edmonson, 2010), dua jenis permintaan setelah bencana terdiri dari tanggap darurat dan pemulihan (Holguín-Veras dan Jaller, 2011), penentuan prioritas jenis bantuan (Destro dan Holguín-Veras, 2011). Peristiwa bencana memerlukan logistik kemanusiaan pasca bencana yang permintaan jauh lebih besar dan lebih kompleks daripada yang diperlukan atau kondisi aman (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). Berbagai situasi yang tidak pasti dengan konsekuensi buruk terhadap potensi kematian korban bencana membutuhkan langkah-langkah kinerja yang tepat dan dapat diandalkan dalam sistem logistik bantuan bencana. Beberapa kasus operasi bantuan bencana di Indonesia telah menghadapi masalah kekurangan komoditas dan pendistribusian bantuan kepada korban.

The main problem in disaster relief logistics, among others unpredictability of demand in terms of timing and location, suddenly-occurring demand in very large amounts and short lead times for a wide variety of supplies, high stakes associated with adequate and timely delivery, lack of resources such as supply, people, technology, transportation capacity, and budget. This should be considered as set constraints. It is necessary that relief supplies are shipped to emergency demand points timely by accurate and reasonable manner in disaster relief operations. Consequently, the availability of commodities and transportation planning is a key of success for effective and efficient distribution. The role of decision support systems are needed to help decision maker's better plan in logistics operations.

The aim of research is develop a system dynamic model to plan the inventory level in humanitarian logistics namely create a computer model as decision support system. The model proposed here aims to coordinate the transportation of commodities from

major supply centres to distribution centres in affected areas. The goal is to minimize delay in providing prioritized commodity.

Literature Review

Several literature reviews in humanitarian logistics have been published in different outlets, and for different audiences. Most of them look at their own background discipline mostly, e.g. Altay and Green (2006) at operations research (and partly operations management), Kovačs and Spens (2007, 2008) mostly at logistics management. Natarajathinam et al. (2009) as well as Peter Tatham's bibliography do well. There is though, an agreement that the operational environment of humanitarian logistics differs from conventional business logistics (Whybark et al., 2010). Main differentiators are its unpredictability of demand (in terms of timing, location, type, and size), surge of demand with a requirement of large quantities but short lead times, the high stakes of adequate and timely delivery, combined with an overall lack of resources (in terms of materials, people, technology, funding, and transportation capacity) (Balcik and Beamon, 2008), and immense scrutiny by the media (Whybark et al., 2010). Many of these factors continue to be the focus of humanitarian logistics research, even though some – e.g. the speed over cost maxim of performance measures – continue to be disputed.

Supply chains link the sources of supply (suppliers) to the owners of demand (end customers). In a typical humanitarian supply chain, governments and NGOs are the primary parties involved. Governments hold the main power with the control they have over political and economical conditions and directly affect supply chain processes with their decisions. After the 2004 tsunami in Aceh, for instance, the Indonesia government did invite international aid agencies to participate at all in the first 60 days of the relief effort, and functioned during that period with the local sources of supplies. Donors, military and the media are the other significant players in the humanitarian supply chains.

Coordination and management of disaster supply chains has challenging problems. The supply network is huge and complicated with numerous players (donors, NGOs, government, military, and suppliers), and it is hard to coordinate all of them along with all the items that need to be delivered. Despite the different cultural, political, geographical and historical differences among them, collaboration and specialization of the tasks between NGOs, military, government and private business are increasingly needed in the humanitarian supply chains (Van Wassenhove, 2006). Despite being experienced and aware of the key points in humanitarian supply chains, people in charge of logistics and supply chain management in most NGOs or other humanitarian organizations are not often specialized in this area, thus they are not experts in the tools for solving the problems that might occur during the operations. There could also be domestic barriers such as the need of excessive paper work, and specific policies of the region that may cause additional delays, as well as external complications due to foreign relations.

Goals and performance metrics of humanitarian and regular supply chains differ notably. Unlike the humanitarian supply chains, which do not have any profit targets and rely heavily on volunteers and donors, in regular supply chains, stakeholders are the owners of the chain. Nevertheless, the numerous models based on minimizing cost (or equivalently, maximizing profit) for building efficient supply chains can be applied to the humanitarian supply chains directly or with modifications. One example is an integrated multi-objective supply chain (SC) model that uses fill rate, cost and flexibility as measurement factors for simultaneous strategic and operational SC planning (Sabri and Beamon, 1999). Lodree and Taskin (2009) work on stochastic production/inventory control models for recovery planning, specifically for hurricanes, to determine how long to postpone decision making to optimize the trade-off between logistics cost efficiency and hurricane forecast accuracy.

Modelling

Humanitarian logistics operate under uncertain, dynamic conditions characterized by urgency, lack of local infrastructure, and rigid funding structures, which render decision-making processes very challenging. People tend to use simple mental models to make decisions based on experience and intuition, even in complex situations, if cause and effect are not clear (causal ambiguity) and occur over time. However, these simple models are not sufficient to capture the whole system. Additionally, human intuition and experience are affected by irrational factors like emotions and time pressure. They are not foolproof, particularly in complex dynamic situations such as those faced by humanitarian logistics system, when one is faced with many time delays and dynamic complexity.

A time delay exists in a process where the output lags behind its input. Dynamic complexity, on the other hand, is due to the many actors that interact strongly with one another and to multiple feedback loops. A feedback loop is a succession of causes and effects such that a change in a given variable travels around the loop and comes back to affect the initiating variable. If an initial increase (or decrease) of a variable in a feedback loop ultimately results in an effect on the same variable in the same direction, then the feedback loop is identified as a positive (self-reinforcing) feedback loop. If an initial increase (or decrease) of a variable ultimately results in an effect on the same variable in the opposite direction, then the feedback loop is identified as a negative (balancing) feedback loop. The feedbacks and delays from the system dynamics methodology are concurrent with characteristics that the humanitarian logistics face like tradeoffs between subsystems and the broader system, and tradeoffs between short term and long term.

Figure 1 Inventory policy in humanitarian logistics system

Figure 1 illustrates three feedback loops very familiar to the humanitarian logistics focusing on development programs. These are driven by interaction between the humanitarian logistics, beneficiaries and donors. The population loop and the food loop are positive, while the donors loop is negative. Specifically in the population loop, an increase in the Population leads, after a specific time delay, to an increase in the Population Growth. This is equal to the discrepancy between the number of deaths and births, and causes a further increase in the Population. Moreover, the Population increases the total Demand for Food.

The behaviour of these two positive loops would lead to the population growing to infinity. Hence, this behaviour is controlled through the negative loop. If in the population and food subsystems we incorporate the donors' expectations, then in the donors loop the donors expect humanitarian organizations to increase the sustainability of the local population over a long-term horizon. System dynamics methodology emerged to capture the interaction of different actors in a system in response to the increasing complexity of organizational objectives and outcomes. It is an effective modelling and simulation methodology for obtaining insights into problems of dynamic complexity and policy resistance.

Figure 2 Simulation model using Powersim Studio 7

To view the many of parameters of the model and their complex relationships, we assume that the behaviour in such systems is in continuous state to facilitate model formulation and its simulation. So the behaviour of the system is not the result of probability; rather is the result of causal loops of variables. In dynamic model, the blocks of the structure of the system are each formulated and modelled using Powersim Studio 7. Mention that the initial values for the level variables are obtained from various references discussions.

Figure 3 Simulation result

Conclusions

Humanitarian decision makers have traditionally relied on their experience and intuition to deal with these challenges. However, experience and intuition are not sufficient particularly in complex and dynamic situations. SD methodology was developed to assist with complex decision making in private sector companies that would impact on the company's operations over time. Specifically, it was developed to study systems characterized by multiple feedback loops, uncertainty, and time lags. The usage of SD methodology has expanded to include social and environmental issues. We suggest that IHO have a number of characteristics that are consistent with the premises of SD. As such, it is therefore an appropriate methodology to capture the complexity of these systems.

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